

Diversity of Fig species and their ecological services in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary, Arunachal Pradesh, India

Dipika Parbo^{1,2}, Awadhesh Kumar^{*2}, Ashalata Devi³, Janmejaya Sethy⁴, Yengkhom Roamer Zest⁵, Rakesh Basnett⁶

^{1,2,5}Wildlife Resource and Conservation Laboratory, Department of Forestry, NERIST, Nirjuli, Arunachal Pradesh, India, 791109

³Department of Environmental Science, Tezpur University, Tezpur, Sonitpur, Assam, India

⁴Amity Institute of Forestry and Wildlife, Amity University, Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

⁶ Forest and Environment Department, Government of Sikkim, East Sikkim, India 737101

*Email: tpileatus@gmail.com

Received: 15 December 2023 / Revised: 12 January 2024 / Accepted: 13 January 2024 / Published online: 13 January 2024.

How to cite: Parbo, D., Kumar, A., Devi, A., Sethy, J., Roamer Zest, Y., Basnett, R. (2024). Diversity of Fig species and their Ecological Services in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary, Arunachal Pradesh, India, *Journal of Wildlife and Biodiversity*, 8(2), 179-205. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11099476>

Abstract

Ficus spp. belongs to the Moraceae family and are primarily found in tropical lowland rainforests. They exhibit various growth types including hemi-epiphytes, climbers, shrubs, and trees. The *Ficus* genus plays a vital role as a keystone species as it significantly impacts its microhabitat and serves as the primary food supply for frugivores throughout the year. Arunachal Pradesh, a state in Northeast India, located in the Eastern Himalayas, comprises a diverse range of forests, including deciduous, evergreen, pine, temperate, alpine, and grassland enriched with a variety of flora and fauna. The current study was conducted in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary, Arunachal Pradesh, to determine the *Ficus* diversity and associated frugivores. The survey was done using 20m X 20m quadrats (41 nos.), which were randomly placed within the sanctuary. *Ficus*-dependent frugivore diversity was examined in their fruiting season using either focal or scan animal sampling techniques by direct sighting. A total of 21 *Ficus* species comprising 482 individuals were recorded, with the highest distribution in the Tipi Range and the lowest in the Pakke Kessang Range. Four habits of *Ficus* species, large trees, small trees, shrubs, and climbers, were documented. There are five sub-genera of *Ficus* that have been recorded. *Ficus semicordata* is the most abundant species, while *F. religiosa* is the least abundant. The frequency percentage of *F. benghalensis* (46.34%) is the highest, and *F. religiosa* (2.44%) is the least, while the density of *F. auriculata* (146.34 ha⁻¹) is the highest, and *F. religiosa* (2.44 ha⁻¹) has the lowest. The highest level of similarity among *Ficus* species is observed between the Tipi and Seijosa Range. The figs of Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary are associated with 54 frugivore species out of them 43 avian and 11 mammalian species.

Keywords: Abundance, Distribution, *Ficus*, Frugivore, Keystone, Morphology

Introduction

Figs (*Ficus spp.*) belonging to the Family Moraceae exhibit a diverse types of habits and growth forms such as hemi-epiphytes, enormous woody climbers as well as trees and shrubs with fruit positions including cauliflory, on the surface of the soil and among leaves (Harrison & Shanahan, 2005; Shanahan et al., 2001). Fig trees have been characterized as the “most distractive of widespread genera of tropical plants”. According to Bagla and Menon (2000), figs are massive trees, that grow to a very great height, and girth with spreading crowns and evergreen barged of tropical lowland rainforest. There are about 755 species of *Ficus spp* worldwide as reported by van Noort and Rasplus (2004-2012). Out of these, 115 taxa (consisting of 89 species and 26 infra-specific taxa) have been recorded to occur in India (Chaudhary et al., 2012). *Ficus spp* are distributed in the tropics and other warm regions of the world, especially in Indo-Malaysia to Australia, Africa and America comprising six subgenera, viz. *Urostigma*, *Pharmacosycea*, *Sycomorus*, *Sycidium*, *Synoecia* and *Ficus* (Berg & Corner, 2005). The distribution of this species in India is primarily concentrated in the North-Eastern States, Peninsular region and Andaman & Nicobar Islands (Chaudhary et al., 2012).

Figs are considered a keystone species for wildlife conservation in tropical forests due to their ability to provide a consistent supply of fruits, flowers, and leaves throughout the year. This is especially important during periods of food scarcity in the habitat. Figs are highly valued by frugivorous animals for their abundant and reliable food resources. Several studies have highlighted the significance of figs in supporting wildlife populations (Barua & Tamuly, 2011; Budiman et al., 2017; Milton, 1991; Ragusa-Netto, 2002; Shanahan et al., 2001). Fig plants thus meet all the necessary criteria to be considered a keystone species: 1) exhibit low redundancy, (2) consumed by a large range of the frugivores, (3) exhibit inter-annual reliability and (4) abundant (Peres, 2000). In addition, the spreading branches of figs with dense foliage also provide shelter to many canopy-dwelling vertebrates or on land surfaces and help to retain moisture under the canopy (Vanitharani et al., 2009).

Being a part of the Eastern Himalayas (one of the 36 Biodiversity Hotspots) and the hills of Northeast India, Arunachal Pradesh is the most biodiverse and largest state among Northeastern states, ranking second largest forest cover state with 66,688 sq. km after Madhya Pradesh (77,482 sq. km) and 4th in terms of percentage of forest cover (79.63%) in India (Indian State of Forest Report, 2019; Mittermeier et al., 2011). The state has 16 protected areas, which include 2 National Parks, 13 Wildlife Sanctuary and 1 Orchid Sanctuary. These protected areas encompass a total area of 9,488.48 sq. km of state forests. Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary (PWLS) is well well-managed

and highly regarded protected area which is surrounded by contiguous forests and undulating terrain and hills on most sides with higher hills in the northern part of sanctuary. PWLS consists of different habitat types, including lowland semi-evergreen, evergreen forest and Eastern Himalayan broadleaf forests. The main vegetation type is classified as Assam Valley tropical semi-evergreen vegetation (Champion & Seth, 1968). A total of 234 plant species (angiosperms) have been recorded with the highest number of species from family *Euphorbiaceae* and *Lauraceae* in PWLS (Dasgupta et al., 2015; Datta & Goyal, 1997; Padmawathe et al., 2004). However, the diversity of figs in the PWLS area has not been thoroughly studied about the assemblage of frugivores. Thus, the main objective of this study was to investigate the diversity of figs in the Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary.

Martial and methods

Study Area

The present study was conducted in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary, situated within the geographical coordinates of longitude 92° 36' - 93° 09' E and latitude 26° 54' - 27° 16' N (Fig. 1). The sanctuary covers an area of 861.95 km², which accounts for 20% of the East Kameng district in Western Arunachal Pradesh (Dasgupta et al., 2015; Datta et al., 2008). The sanctuary is bordered by Bhareli River (also known as Kameng River) in the north and west, Pakke River to the east, and the Nameri National Park and Nauduar Reserve Forest of Assam to the south. PWLS is surrounded by Reserve Forest and other Protected Forests, indicating that it is not an isolated area of forest. The headquarter of the sanctuary is Seijosa, which is 60 km away from Tezpur, a town in Assam, on National Highway - 52 (Dasgupta et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2019). The altitudinal variations starting from 200 to 2040 m above mean sea level. In addition, the area is drained by a number of small rivers and perennial streams of the Bhareli and Pakke Rivers, both of which are tributaries of the Brahmaputra and the main perennial streams are the Nameri, Khari and Upper Dikorai (Datta & Goyal, 1997; Kumar & Solanki, 2008). PWLS exhibits a high level of floral and faunal diversity and serves as a habitat for numerous threatened wild animals (Datta et al., 1998; Datta & Rawat 2008; Kumar & Solanki 2009; Singh, 1991, 1994).

Figure 1. Study area showing sampling points of *Ficus* species in entire Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary

The diversity and population density of fig plants were studied using the quadrats method (Pound & Clements, 1900). Randomly placed quadrats measuring 20m X 20m quadrats were used to sample the area dominated by fig plants in the sanctuary (Schemnitz, 1980). A total of 41 quadrats were laid randomly in the three ranges namely, Pakke Kessang Range, Sejosa Range and Tipi Range having five, 17, and 19 quadrats, respectively. Within each quadrat, the data on the total number of individuals of *Ficus* species, their height, GBH (Girth at Breast Height) and canopy cover were recorded. Photographs of all recorded *Ficus* species were taken, and their identification was done by referring to the 'Flora of Assam' (Kanjilal & Bor, 2005) and consulting the regional herbarium at BSI, Itanagar. The identification of *Ficus* species was done with the assistance of experts from NERIST. During the field survey, the phenophase of each adult fig tree was studied to document the fruiting season and the type of fig. The relationship between *Ficus* species and frugivore species was also explored during the field survey.

The data collected was analyzed for community parameters, such as frequency, density, and abundance as per Curtis and McIntosh (1950). Importance Value Indices (IVI) were calculated for each species by summing up the relative frequency, relative density and relative abundance (Philips, 1959). Based on the number of individuals of a given species, *Ficus* species is categorized

as very rare (single individual), rare (2-10), common (11-25), dominant (26-50) and predominant (>50) as per Kadavul and Parthasarathy (1999). The Jaccard similarity index (Jaccard, 1901) and species diversity index (Shannon & Weiner, 1963) were also calculated. The concentration of dominance was measured following Simpson's index method (Simpson, 1949).

Results

Ficus sp. Distribution

The Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary records a total of 21 species of *Ficus* trees. These trees are distributed among different ranges within the sanctuary. The highest number of *Ficus* trees, with a total of 284 individuals belonging to 19 species, is found in the Tipi Range. The Seijosa Range has 135 individuals belonging to 13 species, while the Pakke Kessang Range has the lowest number of *Ficus* trees, with only 63 individuals belonging to 3 species (Fig. 1, Fig. 2). Two *Ficus* species (*Ficus hirta* and *F. semicordata*) are recorded from all the three ranges. In the Tipi and Pakke Kessang ranges, only one species (*F. auriculata*) is found. However, in the Seijosa and Tipi ranges, nine species are shared (*F. benghalensis*, *F. benjamina*, *F. curtipes*, *F. elastica*, *F. hispida*, *F. geniculata*, *F. drupacea*, *F. microcarpa*, and *F. squamosa*). Seven species (*F. altissima*, *F. cyrtophylla*, *F. glaberrima*, *F. hederacea*, *F. heterophleura*, *F. racemosa* and *F. variegata*) are present only at Tipi Range, whereas two species (*F. religiosa* and *F. rumphii*) are found only at Seijosa range. There are no species that are exclusively found in the Pakke Kessang range. Additionally, there are no species that are shared commonly across the Seijosa and Pakke Kessang range (Fig. 2). Based on total numbers of individual of each species, *Ficus* species is categorized as Predominant (*F. auriculata*, *F. benghalensis*, *F. hirta*, *F. squamosa*), Dominant (*F. curtipes*, *F. elastica*, *F. semicordata*), Common (*F. benjamina*, *F. cyrtophylla*, *F. drupacea*, *F. geniculata*, *F. hispida*), Rare (*F. altissima*, *F. glaberrima*, *F. hederacea*, *F. heteropluera*, *F. microcarpa*, *F. racemosa*, *F. rumphii*, *F. variegata*) and Very Rare (*F. religiosa*) as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. *Ficus* distribution in all three ranges of Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary

Figure 3. *Ficus* distribution in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary

Morphology of *Ficus* species

The *Ficus* species found in the Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary can be classified into five sub-genera such as *Ficus*, *Sycidium*, *Sycomorus*, *Synoecia* and *Urostigma*. Among 21 species, one species each from *Ficus* and *Synoecia* sub-genus, two species from *Sycidium* sub-genus, six species from *Sycomorus* and 11 species from *Urostigma*. The highest canopy coverage observed is 82% for the *F. curtipes*. Additionally, three species (*F. religiosa*, *F. hispida*, *F. squamosa*) are found in open canopy. Among 19 *Ficus* species, GBH of *F. elastica* is found to be highest (1120 cm) and *F. cyrtophylla* is lowest (42 cm). It is worth noting that *F. squamosa* is a shrub while *F. hederacea* is a climber. Considering the height, *F. elastica* is found to be tallest (30 m) while *F. squamosa* recorded shortest growing up to 2 meters (Table 1).

Fig positions of four species (*F. auriculata*, *F. racemosa*, *F. semicordata*, *F. variegata*) are cauliflory, while the other 17 species have axillary fig positions. Maximum number of *Ficus* species has globose fig shape. All figs are soft when they are ripe, with the exception of *F. curtipes*, which are hard. Colour of the fig varies from red to black, and from yellow to green. The length of the Fig of *F. drupacea* is the highest, measuring 4.6 cm, while *F. cyrtophylla* and *F. hederacea* have the lowest length (0.8 cm); *F. auriculata* has the largest diameter (5 cm), *F. cyrtophylla* has smallest diameter, measuring 0.6 cm (Table 1). Leaf arrangements of 18 *Ficus* species are simple, and alternate; two species (*F. hispida*, *F. squamosa*) are simple, and opposite; while *F. hirta* is either simple or compound, alternate. *F. squamosa* is spirally arranged too. Seven species have ovate-elliptic leaf shape, five species have ovate leaf shape and the remaining species leaf shape ranges from cordate to obovate, oblong to elliptic, lanceolate to oblanceolate. The leaf shape of *F. hirta* is either cordate or palmately 3-5 lobed. *F. hirta* have leaves with the largest length (35 cm) and *F. benjamina* have leaves with the smallest length (8 cm) (Table 1).

The recorded *Ficus* species exhibits four types of habits: trees, small trees, shrubs and climbers. The majority of the species in this group are trees (14 species), five species are small trees, one species is shrubs and one species is climber. Based on growth forms, *Ficus* species are divided into two types: hemiepiphytic and non-hemiepiphytic. Twelve species including *F. altissima*, *F. benghalensis*, *F. benjamina*, *F. curtipes*, *F. drupacea*, *F. elastica*, *F. glaberrima*, *F. geniculata*, *F. heteropleura*, *F. macrocarpa*, *F. religiosa* and *F. rumphii*, are hemiepiphytic and are classified as trees; whereas nine species - *F. auriculata*, *F. cyrtophylla*, *F. hederacea*, *F. hirta*, *F. hispida*, *F. racemosa*, *F. semicordata*, *F. squamosa*, *F. variegata* are non-hemiepiphytic, among which two are trees (*F. racemosa*, *F. variegata*), five are small trees (*F. auriculata*, *F. cyrtophylla*, *F. hirta*, *F. hispida*, *F. semicordata*), one is shrub (*F. squamosa*) and one is a climber (*F. hederacea*) (Fig. 5, Fig. 6).

Table 1. Morphological characteristics of *Ficus* species recorded in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary, Arunachal Pradesh

Sl No.	Sub-genus	Species	Canopy	GBH (cm)	Height (m)	Fig characteristics					Fruiting period	Leaf characteristics		
						Position	Shape	Texture (ripe)	Colour	Size (L, D; in cm)		Arrangement	Shape	Length (cm)
1.	<i>Ficus</i>	<i>Ficus hirta</i> Vahl	45%	65	7	Axillary	Globose	Soft	Brownish red	3, 3	Nov-Feb	Simple or compound, alternate	Cordate or palmately 3-5 lobed	34
2.	<i>Sycidium</i>	<i>Ficus cyrtophylla</i> (Miq.) Miq.	10%	42	21	Axillary	Ovoid	Soft	Yellowish green	0.8, 0.6	Sept-Nov	Simple, alternate	Obovate-lanceolate, assymetry	26
3.		<i>Ficus heteropleura</i> Blume	60%	230	12	Axillary	Pear-shaped	Soft	Bright red	0.9, 1	Jan-March	Simple, alternate	Ovate-elliptic	12
4.	<i>Sycomor</i>	<i>Ficus auriculata</i> Lour	60 %	50	8	Cauliflory	Pear-shaped	Soft	Dark red	4, 5	Jan-April	Simple, alternate	Broadly ovate	31
5.		<i>Ficus hispida</i> L.f.	Open	50	3.5	Axillary	Globose	Soft	Pale yellowish green	1.9, 1.8	Dec-June	Simple opposite	Ovate-elliptic	25
6.		<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	50%	420	17	Cauliflory	Pear-shaped	Soft	Deep red	2, 4.1	Oct-Dec	Simple, alternate	Ovate	21
7.		<i>Ficus semicordata</i> Buch.-Ham. ex Sm.	50%	60	5	Cauliflory	Globose	Soft	Dark red	1.4, 1.5	July-Oct	Simple, alternate	Oblong, lanceolate or elliptic, assymetry	27

8.		<i>Ficus squamosa</i> Roxb.	Open	Shrub	2	Axillary	Globose	Soft	Yellowish green	3.4, 3.6	April-July	Simple, opposite, spirally arranged	Oblanceolate	14
9.		<i>Ficus variegata</i> Blume	50%	340	18.5	Cauliflory	Pear-shaped	Soft	Deep red	2.3, 3.7	Oct-Feb	Simple, alternate	Broadly ovate	22
10.	<i>Synoecia</i>	<i>Ficus hederacea</i> Roxb.	44%	Climber	Climber	Axillary	Round	Soft	Bright red	0.8, 0.9	Oct-Feb	Simple, alternate	Ovate	11
11.		<i>Ficus altissima</i> Blume	54%	750	20	Axillary	Ellipsoid	Soft	Reddish yellow	2.3, 2	Jan-June	Simple, alternate	Ovate-elliptic	15
12.		<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	75%	470	25	Axillary	Globose-ellipsoid	Soft	Reddish yellow	3.4, 4.4	May-Aug	Simple, alternate	Ovate	15
13.		<i>Ficus benjamina</i> L.	52%	240	23	Axillary	Globose	Soft	Dark red	2.1, 2.5	Dec-Feb	Simple, alternate	Ovate-lanceolate	8
14.	<i>Urostigma</i>	<i>Ficus curtipes</i> Corner	82%	340	24	Axillary	Globose to depressed globose	Hard	Dark red	1.3, 1.6	Throughout the year	Simple, alternate	Obovate	18
15.		<i>Ficus drupacea</i> Thunb.	60%	1040	26	Axillary	Ellipsoid	Soft	Reddish yellow	4.6, 2.9	Throughout the year	Simple, alternate	Ovate-elliptic	25
16.		<i>Ficus elastica</i> Roxb. ex Hornem.	77%	1120	30	Axillary	Ovoid-ellipsoid	Soft	Yellowish green	1.3, 0.7	Throughout the year	Simple, alternate	Oblong-elliptic	18
17.		<i>Ficus geniculata</i> Kurz	70%	920	24	Axillary	Depressed globose	Soft	Red	1, 1.2	Throughout the year	Simple, alternate	Obovate-oblong	11

18.		<i>Ficus glaberrima</i> Blume	15%	390	17	Axillary	Globose	Soft	Yellow	0.9, 0.9	Dec-Feb	Simple, alternate	Narrowly ovate- elliptic	12
19.		<i>Ficus microcarpa</i> L.f.	80%	370	16	Axillary	Depressed globose	Soft	Greenish yellow	1, 1	Dec-April	Simple, alternate	Ovate- elliptic	10
20.		<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Open	340	24	Axillary	Globose to depressed globose	Soft	Red	1.1, 0.8	Feb-June	Simple, alternate	Broadly ovate- cordiform	14
21.		<i>Ficus rumphii</i> Blume	65%	510	21	Axillary	Globose	Soft	Black	1.4, 0.8	Jan-March	Simple, alternate	Ovate- elliptic	12
Note: GBH - Girth at Breast height; L- Length; D- diameter														

Figure 4. Fruiting Season of the Fig trees

Figure 5. Habits of recorded *Ficus* species

Figure 6. Growth forms of recorded *Ficus* species

Community structure of *Ficus* species

The frequency of the recorded *Ficus* species ranges from 2.44 to 46.34%, density ranges from 0.02 to 1.46 ha⁻¹ and abundance ranges from 1.00 to 29.5. Among 21 *Ficus* species, *Ficus squamosa* (29.5) is the most abundant and *F. religiosa* (1) is least abundant. The frequency of *F. benghalensis* (46.34%) is highest and *F. religiosa* (2.44%) is least, while the density of *F. auriculata* is highest (146.34 ha⁻¹) and *F. religiosa* least (2.44 ha⁻¹) (Table 2). The relative frequency ranges from 0.73 to 13.87, relative density ranges from 0.21 to 12.45, relative abundance ranges from 1.12 to 33.01, and IVI ranges from 2.06 to 46.71. From the calculated values of IVI, *F. squamosa* is found to be highly dominated and *F. religiosa* least dominated (Table 2).

Table 2. Quantitative community parameters of the *Ficus* species recorded in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary

S. No.	Species	Frequency (F %)	Density (ha ⁻¹)	Abundance (A)	RF	RD	RA	IVI
1.	<i>F. auriculata</i>	21.95	146.34	6.67	6.57	12.45	7.46	26.48
2.	<i>F. benghalensis</i>	46.34	124.39	2.68	13.87	10.58	3	27.45
3.	<i>F. benjamina</i>	14.63	39.02	2.67	4.38	3.32	2.98	10.68
4.	<i>F. altissima</i>	04.88	24.39	5.00	1.46	2.07	5.59	9.13
5.	<i>F. curtipes</i>	26.83	65.85	2.45	8.03	5.6	2.75	16.38
6.	<i>F. cyrtophylla</i>	12.20	46.34	3.80	3.65	3.94	4.25	11.84
7.	<i>F. drupacea</i>	19.51	58.54	3.00	5.84	4.98	3.36	14.18
8.	<i>F. elastica</i>	36.59	90.24	2.47	10.95	7.68	2.76	21.39
9.	<i>F. geniculata</i>	19.51	29.27	1.50	5.84	2.49	1.68	10.01
10.	<i>F. glaberrima</i>	07.32	14.63	2.00	2.19	1.24	2.24	5.67
11.	<i>F. hederacea</i>	04.88	07.32	1.50	1.46	0.62	1.68	3.76
12.	<i>F. heteropluera</i>	09.76	14.63	1.50	2.92	1.24	1.68	5.84
13.	<i>F. hirta</i>	14.63	136.59	9.33	4.38	11.62	10.44	26.44
14.	<i>F. hispida</i>	19.51	39.02	2.00	5.84	3.32	2.24	11.40
15.	<i>F. macrocarpa</i>	14.63	24.39	1.67	4.38	2.07	1.86	8.32
16.	<i>F. racemosa</i>	04.88	12.2	2.50	1.46	1.04	2.80	5.29
17.	<i>F. religiosa</i>	02.44	2.44	1.00	0.73	0.21	1.12	2.06
18.	<i>F. rumphii</i>	14.63	19.51	1.33	4.38	1.66	1.49	7.53
19.	<i>F. semicordata</i>	24.39	117.07	4.80	7.30	9.96	5.37	22.63
20.	<i>F. squamosa</i>	04.88	143.9	29.5	1.46	12.24	33.01	46.71
21.	<i>F. variegata</i>	09.76	19.51	2.00	2.92	1.66	2.24	6.82

***Ficus* Diversity**

Shannon Weiner Diversity Index of *Ficus* species in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary is 2.69 (Fig. 7). According to Shannon Weiner Diversity Index (H), Tipi range is most diverse with 19 *Ficus* species exhibiting H value 3.3, followed by Seijosa Range with 13 *Ficus* species (H=2.24) and Pakke Kessang least diverse with 03 *Ficus* species (H=0.71) (Fig. 7). Similarly, from Simpson index it is recorded that *Ficus* species diversity is highest in Tipi Range (1-λ

=0.92) and lowest dominance value with $\lambda = 0.09$, whereas Pakke Kessang Range have lowest *Ficus* diversity ($1 - \lambda = 0.49$) and highest dominance ($\lambda = 0.51$) among the three ranges of PWS. Thus, there is about 92% chance that two randomly selected individuals from the Tipi Range would be from different species and 9% chance that the two randomly selected individuals would be from same species (Fig. 8).

Figure 7. Shannon-Weiner diversity index of *Ficus* species

Figure 8. Simpson diversity index of *Ficus* species

After comparing the three ranges of Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary (Seijosa Range, Tipi Range, and Pakke Kessang Range) using the Jaccard Similarity Index and Jaccard Distance Index, it was found that the highest similarity in *Ficus* species is between Tipi Range and Seijosa Range (0.524). The next highest similarity is between Tipi Range and Pakke Kessang Range (0.158), and the lowest similarity is between Pakke Kessang Range and Seijosa Range (0.118), as shown in Table 3(a). In the contrary, the highest dissimilarity is observed between the Pakke Kessang Range and the Seijosa Range (0.882), followed by the similarity between the Tipi Range and the Pakke Kessang Range (0.842), and the lowest similarity appears between the Tipi Range and the Seijosa Range (0.476) according to Table 3(b).

Table 3(a): Jaccard Similarity Index for similarity of *Ficus* species among the three ranges of Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary- Seijosa Range, Tipi Range and Pakke Kessang Range

	Seijosa Range	Tipi Range	Pakke Kessang Range
Seijosa Range	1	0.524	0.118
Tipi Range	0.524	1	0.158
Pakke Kessang Range	0.118	0.158	1

Table 3(b): Jaccard Distance for the dissimilarity of *Ficus* species among the three ranges of Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary- Seijosa Range, Tipi Range and Pakke Kessang Range

	Seijosa Range	Tipi Range	Pakke Kessang Range
Seijosa Range	1	0.476	0.882
Tipi Range	0.476	1	0.842
Pakke Kessang Range	0.882	0.842	1

Figs as keystone species

As a keystone species, 16 out of 21 *Ficus* species of Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary are found consumed by a large number of frugivores, including birds and mammals. *F. benghalensis* is found supporting the highest species number of frugivore i.e. 32 species, followed by *F. geniculata* and *F. drupacea* supporting 31 and 30 frugivore species respectively, and only four Frugivore species depend on *F. hirta*, which is least. Five *Ficus* species, *F. auriculata*,

F. cyrtophylla, *F. hederacea*, *F. racemosa* and *F. squamosa* are found not supporting any frugivore (Fig. 9). A total of 54 frugivore species with 1131 individuals are documented being supported by *Ficus* species of PWLS; of which 43 species (942 individuals) are avian and 11 species (189 individuals) are mammalian species. Among 43 avian species, 27 genera and 15 families have been recorded. Similarly, 11 mammalian species have 10 genera and six families. Among avian species, *Pycnonotus flaviventris* is found to be visiting the highest number of *Ficus* species, 11 species. On the other hand, *Anthracoceros albirostris*, *Treron curvirostra*, *Sturnia malabarica*, *Oriolus traillii*, *Chloropsis hardwickii* and *Yuhina flavicollis* each are supported by only one *Ficus* species. Whereas among mammals, *Muntiacus muntjak* is associated with 13 *Ficus* species, while *Pteropus giganteus leucocephalus* visits only *Ficus drupacea* (Table. 4).

Figure 9. Number of frugivores depending on *Ficus* species

Table 4: Association of *Ficus* species with the recorded individuals of frugivore species

Frugivore Species				Associated <i>Ficus</i> Species	
Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	No. of Individuals	No. of Species	Scientific Name
Birds					
Bucerotidae	<i>Anthracoceros albirostris</i>	Oriental Pied Hornbill	5	1	<i>F. drupacea</i>
	<i>Buceros bicornis</i>	Great Hornbill	17	5	<i>F. benghalensis, F. benjamina, F. curtipes, F. drupacea, F. geniculata</i>
	<i>Rhyticeros undulates</i>	Wreathed Hornbill	8	3	<i>F. drupacea, F. geniculata, F. macrocarpa</i>
Chloropseidae	<i>Chloropsis aurifrons</i>	Golden Fronted Leafbird	15	2	<i>F. geniculata, F. macrocarpa</i>
	<i>Chloropsis hardwickii</i>	Orange Bellied Leafbird	6	1	<i>F. geniculata</i>
Columbidae	<i>Chalcophaps indica</i>	Emerald Dove	36	3	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. elastica</i>
	<i>Ducula aenea</i>	Green Imperial Pigeon	14	3	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Ducula badia</i>	Mountain Imperial Pigeon	11	2	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea</i>
	<i>Treron apicauda</i>	Pintailed Green Pigeon	28	4	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. geniculata, F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Treron curvirostra</i>	Thickbilled Green Pigeon	5	1	<i>F. benghalensis</i>
	<i>Treron phoenicoptera</i>	Yellow Footed Green Pigeon	27	4	<i>F. benghalensis, F. elastica, F. geniculata, F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Treron sphenurus</i>	Wedgetailed Green Pigeon	15	4	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. geniculata, F. rumphii</i>
Cuculidae	<i>Cuculus Micropterus</i>	Indian Cuckoo	12	4	<i>F. benghalensis, F. benjamina, F. drupacea, F. geniculata</i>
Dicruridae	<i>Dicrurus aeneus</i>	Bronze Drongo	8	2	<i>F. hispida, F. religiosa</i>
	<i>Dicrurus hottentottus</i>	Hair Crested Drongo	14	4	<i>F. benghalensis, F. curtipes, F. geniculata, F. macrocarpa</i>
	<i>Dicrurus leucophaeus</i>	Ashy Drongo	15	3	<i>F. glaberrima, F. microcarpa, F. religiosa</i>

	<i>Dicrurus paradiseus</i>	Greater Racket Tailed Drongo	9	3	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. geniculata</i>
	<i>Dicrurus remifer</i>	Lesser Racket Tailed Drongo	10	3	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. geniculata</i>
Irenidae	<i>Irena puella</i>	Asian Ferry Blue Bird	32	3	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. macrocarpa</i>
Muscicapidae	<i>Myophonus caeruleus</i>	Blue Whistling Thrush	13	2	<i>F. elastica, F. macrocarpa</i>
Oriolidae	<i>Oriolus traillii</i>	Maroon Oriole	14	1	<i>F. geniculata</i>
	<i>Oriolus xanthornus</i>	Black Hooded Oriole	17	2	<i>F. geniculata, F. macrocarpa</i>
Phasianidae	<i>Gallus gallus</i>	Red Jungle Fowl	18	9	<i>F. benghalensis, F. altissima, F. drupacea, F. elastica, F. geniculata, F. glaberrima, F. hirta, F. hispida, F. semicordata</i>
	<i>Lophura leucomelanos</i>	Kalij Pheasant	8	3	<i>F. altissima, F. drupacea, F. semicordata</i>
	<i>Polyplectron bicalcaratum</i>	Grey Peacock Pheasant	4	2	<i>F. altissima, F. semicordata</i>
Pycnonotidae	<i>Alophoixus flaveolus</i>	White Throated Bulbul	10	3	<i>F. drupacea, F. elastica, F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Hemixos flavala</i>	Ashy Bulbul	26	3	<i>F. elastica, F. geniculata, F. heteropleura</i>
	<i>Hypsipetes leucocephalus</i>	Black Bulbul	40	5	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. elastica, F. geniculata, F. heteropleura</i>
	<i>Ixos mccllellandii</i>	Mountain Bulbul	14	2	<i>F. drupacea, F. elastica</i>
	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	Red Vented Bulbul	70	7	<i>F. benghalensis, F. elastica, F. geniculata, F. hispida, F. microcarpa, F. religiosa, F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Pycnonotus flaviventris</i>	Black Crested Bulbul	97	11	<i>F. benghalensis, F. benjamina, F. curtipes, F. drupacea, F. elastica, F. geniculata, F. glaberrima, F. heteropleura, F. hispida, F. microcarpa, F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i>	Red whiskered bulbul	16	2	<i>F. benghalensis, F. microcarpa,</i>
Ramphastidae	<i>Psilopogon asiaticus</i>	Blue Throated barbet	78	9	<i>F. benghalensis, F. benjamina, F. curtipes, F. drupacea, F. elastica, F.</i>

					<i>geniculata</i> , <i>F. glaberrima</i> , <i>F. microcarpa</i> , <i>F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Psilopogon cyanotis</i>	Blue Eared Barbet	38	6	<i>F. benghalensis</i> , <i>F. curtipes</i> , <i>F. geniculata</i> , <i>F. glaberrima</i> , <i>F. heteropluera</i> , <i>F. hispida</i>
	<i>Psilopogon lineatus</i>	Lineated Barbet	38	5	<i>F. benghalensis</i> , <i>F. drupacea</i> , <i>F. elastica</i> , <i>F. geniculata</i> , <i>F. microcarpa</i>
	<i>Psilopogon virens</i>	Great Barbet	18	3	<i>F. benjamina</i> , <i>F. curtipes</i> , <i>F. elastica</i>
Sturnidae	<i>Acridotheres fuscus</i>	Jungle Myna	28	3	<i>F. benghalensis</i> , <i>F. benjamina</i> , <i>F. elastica</i>
	<i>Acridotheres grandis</i>	Great Myna	17	2	<i>F. benghalensis</i> , <i>F. microcarpa</i>
	<i>Gracula religiosa</i>	Common Hill Myna	54	8	<i>F. benghalensis</i> , <i>F. benjamina</i> , <i>F. curtipes</i> , <i>F. drupacea</i> , <i>F. geniculata</i> , <i>F. heteropluera</i> , <i>F. microcarpa</i> , <i>F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Sturnia malabarica</i>	Chestnut Tailed Starling	9	1	<i>F. macrocarpa</i>
Trogonidae	<i>Harpactes erythrocephalus</i>	Red Headed Trogon	12	3	<i>F. benghalensis</i> , <i>F. elastica</i> , <i>F. geniculata</i>
Turdidae	<i>Cochoa viridis</i>	Green Cochoa	11	2	<i>F. benjamina</i> , <i>F. variegata</i>
Zosteropidae	<i>Yuhina flavicollis</i>	Whiskered Yuhina	5	1	<i>F. geniculate</i>
Mammals					
Cercopithecidae	<i>Macaca assamensis</i>	Assamese Macaque	49	4	<i>F. drupacea</i> , <i>F. geniculata</i> , <i>F. heteropleura</i> , <i>F. hirta</i>
	<i>Macaca mulata</i>	Rhesus Macaque	43	6	<i>F. curtipes</i> , <i>F. drupacea</i> , <i>F. geniculata</i> , <i>F. hirta</i> , <i>F. hispida</i> , <i>F. religiosa</i>
Cervidae	<i>Muntiacus muntjac</i>	Barking Deer	17	13	<i>F. benghalensis</i> , <i>F. benjamina</i> , <i>F. altissima</i> , <i>F. drupacea</i> , <i>F. geniculata</i> , <i>F. glaberrima</i> , <i>F. heteropleura</i> , <i>F. hispida</i> , <i>F. microcarpa</i> , <i>F. religiosa</i> , <i>F. semicordata</i> , <i>F. variegata</i> , <i>F. rumphii</i>

	<i>Rusa unicolor</i>	Sambar	9	6	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. geniculata, F. microcarpa, F. semicordata, F. variegata</i>
Pteropodidae	<i>Pteropus giganteus leucocephalus</i>	Indian Flying Fox	2	1	<i>F. drupacea</i>
Sciuridae	<i>Callosciurus pygerythrus</i>	Hoary Bellied Squirrel	26	11	<i>F. benjamina, F. altissima, F. elastica, F. geniculata, F. glaberrima, F. heteropleura, F. hirta, F. hispida, F. religiosa, F. variegata, F. rumphii</i>
	<i>Ratufa bicolor</i>	Himalayan Giant Squirrel	11	7	<i>F. benghalensis, F. altissima, F. drupacea, F. geniculata, F. microcarpa, F. religiosa, F. rumphii</i>
Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	Wild Boar	5	3	<i>F. benghalensis, F. semicordata, F. variegata</i>
Viverridae	<i>Arctitis binturong</i>	Binturong	8	3	<i>F. benghalensis, F. drupacea, F. geniculata</i>
	<i>Paguma larvata</i>	Himalayan Palm Civet	10	5	<i>F. benghalensis, F. altissima, F. drupacea, F. geniculata, F. semicordata</i>
	<i>Parodoxurus hemaphroditus</i>	Common Palm Civet	9	4	<i>F. benghalensis, F. altissima, F. drupacea, F. semicordata</i>

Discussion

The Eastern Himalayas of India have always been rich in biodiversity with its high highly diverse flora and fauna, unique germplasm, and endemic species. Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary of Arunachal Pradesh is enriched with high biodiversity with a higher level of taxonomic diversity. A study conducted in Arunachal Pradesh documented the presence of over 40 species of *Ficus* (Giri et al., 2008). Arunachal Pradesh has a recorded number of over 70 species of plants from the Moraceae family, which are classified into six genera: *Artocarpus*, *Broussonetia*, *Ficus*, *Maclura*, *Morus*, and *Streblus*. Among these, *Ficus* has the highest number of species, with a total of 51 (Buragohain, 2014; Singh & Hage, 2017) documented four *Ficus* species (*F. auriculata*, *F. hispida*, *F. semicordata*, *F. subulata*) from eight districts of Arunachal Pradesh including Lower Subansiri, Lower Dibang valley, Upper Subansiri, Kra Dadi, Papumpare, West Siang, Tawang and Tirap. Bhuyan and Pangu (2020) recorded 11 *Ficus* species from East Kameng district of Arunachal Pradesh – *F. auriculata*, *F. benghalensis*, *F. benjamina*, *F. dumosa*, *F. elastica*, *F. elmeri*, *F. fistulosa*, *F. hirta*, *F. hispida*, *F. racemosa* and *F. rumphii*. According to Kumar (2006), four *Ficus* species serve as food plants for Capped Langur (*Trachypithecus pileatus*) in Pakhui Wildlife Sanctuary. A total of 165 species were enumerated from Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary with 1,899 trees, of which 128 species are identified with 51 families and 37 species are unidentified. Twelve species out of 128 identified species belong to Moraceae family, of which 10 species are from the genus *Ficus*, one is from *Artocarpus* and one is from *Morus*; and two species out of unidentified 37 species are from the genus *Ficus* (Dutta & Rawat, 2008). Out of these 10 *Ficus* species, three species, *F. altissima*, *F. cyrtophylla*, and *F. elastica* are recorded in the present study with varying number of individuals. In 2012, Devi, et al., has noted one species, *Ficus racemosa*, from Pakke Tiger Reserve; whereas Tag et al. (2012) documented almost 215 species of higher plants belonging to 165 genera and 70 families. Out of these 215 species, there were five species of *Ficus*, all of which are recorded in the present study. Balkrishna et al. (2022) mentioned six *Ficus* species in the Seijosa circle to be used for various indigenous purposes. Gogoi et al. (2023) also documented five *Ficus* species, viz. *F. altissima*, *F. drupacea*, *F. geniculata*, *F. nervosa* and *F. variegata* from PWLS. In the present study, a total of 21 *Ficus* species are documented from Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary with 482 individuals. The recorded species in the present study are found to be higher in number than (Kumar, 2006; Dutta and Rawat, 2008; Devi et al., 2012; Tag et al., 2012; Balkrishna et al., 2022; Gogoi et al., 2023) (Table 5).

Table 5 Reference table for identification of figs species.

Sl. Nos.	<i>Ficus</i> species	References
1.	<i>F.altissima</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008; Balkrishna <i>et al.</i> 2022; Gogoi <i>et al.</i> 2023; Present Study
2.	<i>F.auriculata</i>	Present Study
3.	<i>F. benghalensis</i>	Kumar 2006; Tag <i>et al.</i> 2012; Present Study
4.	<i>F.benjamina</i>	Balkrishna <i>et al.</i> 2022; Present Study
5.	<i>F.curtipes</i>	Present Study
6.	<i>F.cyrtophylla</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008; Present Study
7.	<i>F.drupacea</i>	Gogoi <i>et al.</i> 2023; Present Study
8.	<i>F.elastica</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008; Tag <i>et al.</i> 2012; Balkrishna <i>et al.</i> 2022; Present Study
9.	<i>F.geniculata</i>	Gogoi <i>et al.</i> 2023; Present Study
10.	<i>F.glaberrima</i>	Present Study
11.	<i>F.glomerata</i>	Kumar 2006
12.	<i>F.hederacea</i>	Present Study
13.	<i>F.heteropluera</i>	Present Study
14.	<i>F.hirta</i>	Present Study
15.	<i>F.hispida</i>	Tag <i>et al.</i> 2012; Balkrishna <i>et al.</i> 2022; Present Study
16.	<i>F.hookeri</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008
17.	<i>F.lamponga</i>	Kumar 2006; Dutta and Rawat 2008
18.	<i>F.maccllelandi</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008
19.	<i>F.macrocarpa</i>	Present Study
20.	<i>F.mysorensis</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008
21.	<i>F.nervosa</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008; Gogoi <i>et al.</i> 2023
22.	<i>F.pomifera</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008
23.	<i>F.racemosa</i>	Devi <i>et al.</i> 2012; Present Study
24.	<i>F.religiosa</i>	Kumar 2006; Balkrishna <i>et al.</i> 2022; Present Study
25.	<i>F.rumphii</i>	Present Study
26.	<i>F.semicordata</i>	Balkrishna <i>et al.</i> 2022; Present Study
27.	<i>F. scandens</i>	Dutta and Rawat 2008
28.	<i>Ficus squamosa</i>	Present Study
29.	<i>Ficus variegata</i>	Gogoi <i>et al.</i> 2023; Present Study

Ficus species are often observed in human dominated areas. For those species are considered in associations with religious factors for example *F. benghalensis*, *F. religiosa*, *F. virens* (Barua & Tamuly, 2011). In PWLS too *F. religiosa* and *F. hispida* are observed only in human dominated areas surrounding the Sanctuary. Shu (2003) mentioned the plants of *Ficus* species vary greatly in habits from trees to shrubs, climbers to stranglers, or sometimes woody epiphytes. According to Harrison and Shanahan (2005), the *Ficus* comprises of enormous woody climbers, trees and shrubs along with strangling plants. Most of the *Ficus* plants from the present study are trees (14 species), the small trees (five species) and very few are shrubs (one species) and climber (one species). Twelve species are hemiepiphytic, which are all trees. Among nine non-hemiepiphytic species, two are trees, five are small trees, one is shrub, and one is climber (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). Kattan and Valenzuela (2013) observed five *Ficus* species (*F. mutisii*, *F. andicola*, *F. hartwegii*, *F. killipi* and *F. aff. cuatrecasana*) at Otun Quimbaya Flora and Fauna.

Sanctuary of the Andes of Colombia produces ripe figs throughout the year whose availability varied to an extent, from the least fig production of one individual per species in August and September to the highest of 10 individuals per species in March. Maximum of the fruiting species in tropical areas tend to bear fruits either at the peak rainy season or just before its onset (David et al., 2012; Lieberman, 1982; Murali & Sukumar, 1994; Sundarapandian et al., 2005). Whereas the figs (*Ficus*) do not fruit seasonally and are available. On studying the fruiting phenology of four fig species *Ficus benghalensis*, *F. amplissima*, *F. microcarpa* and *F. racemosa* in Sriharikota of Andhra Pradesh, India, the lowest in December and January and the highest number of individuals with ripe figs were in April, November and May (David et al., 2012). In Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary, the fruiting period of most of the *Ficus* species, like *F. curtipes*, *F. drupacea*, *F. elastica*, *F. geniculata*, is not confined to one particular season of a year. Instead, different individuals of a particular *Ficus* species bear fruits at different times of the year, providing food for wild animals throughout the year. Few *Ficus* species like *F. auriculata*, *F. squamosa* are found fruiting in one particular season of the year. For example, *F. auriculata* is found fruiting from October to January and *F. squamosa* from May to August (Fig. 4, Table 1).

Figs (*Ficus* spp.) are always considered as 'Keystone species' of tropical forests, because they have the capacity to produce abundant and constant figs and other food resources (flowers and leaves) throughout the year unlike any other plant groups (Milton, 1991; Peres, 2000; Ragusa-Netto, 2002; Shanahan et al., 2001). In PWLS the documented *Ficus* species feeds the 43 bird species and 11 mammal species the whole year. Shanahan et al., (2001) specified over 1200 species of birds and mammals: over 10% of world's bird species and 6% of mammals prominently feed on figs. Kattan and Valenzuela (2013) observed 36 avian and three mammalian frugivores feeding on three species of figs (*F. andicola*, *killipaa* and *F. mutisii*) in Otun Quimbaya Flora and Fauna Sanctuary, Columbia.

Barua and Tamuly (2011) recorded 67 species of avian frugivores depending on five *Ficus* species, *F. religiosa*, *F. virens*, *F. rutusa*, *F. benghalensis* and *F. racemosa* around Kaziranga National Park and Panbari Reserve Forest, Golaghat, Assam. Vanitharani et al. (2009) discussed the dependency of 30 bird species, 12 species of bats and 17 species of mammals on 18 *Ficus* species for, as feeders as well as habitat users. Daru et al. (2015) too witnessed 12 *Ficus* species associated with 48 bird species at Amurum Forest Reserve. Ragusa-Netto (2002) observed 12 birds species depending on *F. calyptroceras*, while Budiman et al. (2017) observed three hornbill species (*Anthroceros albirostris*, *Anthroceros malayanus*, *Buceros rhinoceros*) on *F. crassiramea*. In PWLS Gogoi et al. (2023) documented 54 vertebrate species (43 birds and 11 mammals) surviving on *Ficus drupacea*, *Ficus geniculata*, *Ficus altissima* and *Ficus variegata*. Only 16 *Ficus* species out of 21 are found to be associated with 54 frugivore species - 43 avian species and 11 mammalian species. *F. benghalensis* is found most preferred food source being visited by 32 frugivore species and *F. hirta* is least visited with four frugivore species. Pothasin et al. (2014) mentioned *F. squamosa*, along with 33 other *Ficus* species, as a riparian species. *F. squamosa* of PWLS is documented to be fruiting from April to July, which lies in the monsoon period. Thus, the species happens to be either washed away or covered by the flood water leaving no chance for any frugivore to feed on.

Conclusion

In PWLS *Ficus* species plays a very important role as food source for the 54 species of both mammalian and avian frugivores. The three ranges of the sanctuary have different distribution, and abundance of *Ficus* species, with the Tipi range having the highest diversity and Pakke Kesang Range least. Except *F. curtipes*, every document species has soft ripe figs. Few species have no canopy cover while maximum have canopy of 10%– 82%. Fruiting of figs does not depend on the season of the year; only four species bear figs throughout the year, and all different individuals of same species may bear figs in different periods of the year. Thus, by attracting a diverse range of frugivores for sustenance, refuge, and various other behaviors year-round, the species serves a keystone species of PWLS. Consequently, these frugivores may aid in the dispersal of fig seeds, contributing to conservation efforts within the sanctuary.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the Principal Chief Conservator of Forest, Wildlife, Itanagar for providing us the necessary permit to carry out our research, the Divisional Forest Officers and Range Forest Officers, Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary for their support throughout our field work. Our special thanks to STPFs and other forest personnel for helping us with our data collection. We are also thankful to the Director,

NERIST and Head, Department of Forestry, NERIST, Arunachal Pradesh for their administrative supports. We are also thankful to our family members for their support.

Declaration of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The authors are solely responsible for the content and writing of the paper.

References

- Bagla, P., & Menon, S. (2000). Trees of India. Timeless books. The Art Book Studio, New Delhi.
- Balkrishna, A., Joshi, B., Srivastava, A., Shukla, B. K., Shankar, R., Kumar, A., Aqib, Kumar, A., Prajapati, U. B., & Mishra, R. K. (2022). Indigenous Uses of Plants among Forest-dependent Communities of Seijosa, Arunachal Pradesh. *International Journal of Economic Plants*, 9(1), 064-080. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.23910/2/2022.0450>
- Barua, M., & Tamuly, J. (2011). Conservation of Figs and Frugivores in Assam, India. Final Project Report to the Rufford Small Grants Program (UK).
- Berg, C. C., & Corner, E. J. H. (2005). Moraceae (*Ficus*). In: Noteboom, H. P. (eds.), Flora Malesiana. National Herbarium of Nederland, Leiden, the Netherlands, Series 1. Pp: 17(2), 1–730.
- Bhuyan, L. R., & Pangu, Y. (2020). Preliminary report on the forest flora of East Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh. *Bulletin of Arunachal Forest Research*, 35(1&2), 29-43
- Budiman, Wijayanti, A., & Lumaby, R. (2017). The Role of *Ficus crassiramea* (Miq.) Miq. for Hornbill Conservation in Borneo Fragmented Tropical Rainforest. In ICBS Conference Proceedings, International Conference on Biological Science (2015), *KnE Life Sciences*, 61–69.
- Buragohain, R. (2014). Studies on taxonomic diversity and socioeconomic value of Moraceae in Arunachal Pradesh. PhD Thesis, Department of Forestry, Northeastern Regional Institute of Science and Technology.
- Champion, H. G., & Seth, S. K. (1968). A revised survey of the forest types of India. Government of India Press, New Delhi, 404.
- Chaudhary, L. B., Sudhakar, J.V., Kumar, A., Bajpai, O., Tiwari, R., & Murthy, G. V. S. (2012). Synopsis of the Genus *Ficus* L. (Moraceae) in India. *Taiwania*, 57, 193–216.
- Curtis, J. T., & McIntosh, R. P. (1950). The Interrelations of Certain Analytic and Synthetic Phytosociological Characters. *Ecology*, 31(3), 434-455.
- Daru, B. H., Yessoufou, K., Nuttman, C., & Abalaka, J. (2015). A preliminary study of bird use of fig *Ficus* species in Amurum Forest Reserve, Nigeria. *Malimbus*, 37.
- Dasgupta, S., Choudhury, P., Ashraf, N. V. K., Bhattacharjee, P. C., & Kyarong, S. (2015). Food Preference of Rehabilitated Asiatic Black Bear cubs in Lowland Tropical Forests of Northeast India. *Asian Journal of Conservation Biology*, 4(1), 20-25.
- Datta, A., & Goyal, S. P. (1997). Response of arboreal mammals to selective logging in western Arunachal Pradesh. Draft report submitted to Wildlife Institute of India, Dehradun.
- Datta, A., & Rawat, G. S. (2008). Dispersal modes and spatial patterns of tree species in a tropical forest in Arunachal Pradesh, Northeast India. *Tropical Conservation Science*, 1(3), 163-185.
- Datta, A., Singh, P., Athreya, R. M., & Karthikeyan, S. (1998). Birds of Pakhui Wildlife Sanctuary in western Arunachal Pradesh. *Newsletter for Birdwatchers*, 38 (6), 91-96.

- Datta, A., Naniwadekar, R., & Anand, M. O. (2008). Hornbills, hoolocks and hog badgers: long-term monitoring of threatened wildlife with local communities in Arunachal Pradesh, Northeast India. Final report to the Rufford Small Grants Program (UK). Nature Conservation Foundation, Mysore, India, 80.
- David, J. P., Murugan, B. S., & Manakadan, R. (2012). Seasonality in fruiting of fig and non-fig species in a tropical dry evergreen forest in Sriharikota Island, southern India. *Tropical Ecology*, 53 (1), 1-13.
- Devi, N., Sarma, G. C., & Baishya, S. K. (2012). Wild Edible Fruits of Pakke Tiger Reserve in Arunachal Pradesh, India. *Pleione*, 6(2), 348 - 352.
- Gogoi, A. P., Sethy, J., Kumar, A., Parbo, D., Chatakonda, M. K., & Maletha, A. (2023). Vertebrate assemblages on fruiting figs in the Indian eastern Himalaya's Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary. *Journal of Threatened Taxa*, 15(10), 23977–23989. <https://doi.org/10.11609/jott.8549.15.10.23977-23989>
- Indian State of Forest Report (2019). Forest Survey of India, Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change, Edition 16, Volume I, pp 185
- Giri, G. S., Pramanik, A. & Chowdhery, H. J. (2008). Material for the Flora of Arunachal Pradesh, Vol. 2 (Asteraceae – Ceratophyllaceae). Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata, 388-407
- Harrison, R. D., & Shanahan, M. (2005). Seventy-seven ways to be a fig: An overview of a diverse assemblage of figs in Borneo. In: Roubik, D. W., Sakai, S. and Hamid, A. A. (Eds.), *Pollination Ecology and the Rain Forest Canopy: Sarawak Studies*. Springer Verlag, New York, 111–127.
- Jaccard, P. (1901). Distribution de la flore alpine dans le Bassin des Drouces et dans quelques regions voisines. *Bulletin de la Société Vaudoise des Sciences Naturelles*, 37(140), 241–272. DOI: [10.5169/seals-266440](https://doi.org/10.5169/seals-266440)
- Kadavul, K., & Parthasarathy, N. (1999). Plant biodiversity and conservation of tropical semi-evergreen forest in the Shervarayan hills of Eastern Ghats, India. *Biodiversity & Conservation*, 8(3), 419–437.
- Kanjilal, U. N., & Bor, N. L. (2005). *Flora of Assam*. Omsons Publications, New Delhi.
- Kattan, G. H., & Valenzuela, L. A. (2013). Phenology, abundance and consumers of figs (*Ficus* spp.) in a tropical cloud forest: evaluation of a potential keystone resource. *Journal of Tropical Ecology*, 29(05), 401–407. DOI:10.1017/s0266467413000461
- Kumar, A. (2006). Studies on ecological and behavioural aspects of capped langur, *Trachypithecus pileatus* (Blyth 1843) in Pakhui Wildlife Sanctuary, Arunachal Pradesh, India. Ph.D. thesis, North Eastern Hill University, Meghalaya, India.
- Kumar, A., & Solanki, G. S. (2008). Population Status and Conservation of Capped Langurs (*Trachypithecus pileatus*) in and around Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary, Arunachal Pradesh, India. *Primate Conservation*, 23, 97–105.
- Kumar, A., & Solanki, G. S. (2009). Cattle-Carnivore Conflict: A Case Study of Pakke Tiger Reserve in Arunachal Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Ecology and Environmental Science*, 35(1), 121–127.
- Kumar, A., Krishna, M., Devi, A., Tapi, T., Rayem, S., & Nabum, T. (2019). Project report on Exploring Wildlife and Nature Based Tourism as a Potential Livelihood Option for Local People inhabiting in and around the Protected Areas in Eastern Himalayas, Arunachal Pradesh: A Sustainable approach for biodiversity conservation. NMHS Funded Project.
- Lieberman, D. (1982). Seasonality and Phenology in a Dry Tropical Forest in Ghana. *The Journal of Ecology*, 70(3), 791. DOI:10.2307/2260105

- Milton, K. (1991). Leaf change and fruit production in six neotropical Moraceae species. *The Journal of Ecology*, 79, 1-26.
- Mittermeier, R. A., Turner, W. R., Larsen, F. W., Brooks, T. M., & Gascon, C. (2011). Global Biodiversity Conservation: The critical role of hotspots. In: Zachos, F. E. and Habel, J. C. (Eds.), *Biodiversity Hotspots: Distribution and protection of conservation priority areas*. Springer, Berlin Heidelberg, 3-22.
- Murali, K. S., & Sukumar, R. (1994). Reproductive Phenology of a Tropical Dry Forest in Mudumalai, Southern India. *The Journal of Ecology*, 82(4), 759. DOI:10.2307/2261441
- Padmawathe, R., Qureshi, Q., & Rawat, G. S. (2004). Effects of selective logging on vascular epiphyte diversity in a moist lowland forest of Eastern Himalaya, India. *Biological Conservation*, 119, 81– 92.
- Peres, C. A. (2000). Identifying keystone plant resources in tropical forests: the case of gums from *Parkia* pods. *Journal of Tropical Ecology*, 16, 287-317.
- Phillips, E. A. (1959). *Methods of vegetation study*. New York, NY: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Pothasin, P., Compton, S. G., & Wangpakapattanawong, P. (2014). Riparian Ficus Tree Communities: The Distribution and Abundance of Riparian Fig Trees in Northern Thailand. *PLOS ONE*, 9, 10.
- Pound, R., & Clements, F. E. (1900). *Phytogeography of Nebraska*, 2nd edition, 61-63.
- Ragusa-Netto, J. (2002). Fruiting phenology and consumption by birds in *Ficus calyptroceras* (Miq.) Miq. (Moraceae). *Brazilian Journal of Biology*, 62, 339–346.
- Schemnitz, S. D. (1980). *Wildlife Management Technique Manual*. Wildlife Society, Washington D.C., USA.
- Shu, R. (2003). *FICUS* Linnaeus. *Flora of China*, 5, 37-71.
- Shanahan, M., So, S., Compton, S. G., & Corlett, R. (2001). Fig-eating by vertebrate frugivores: A Global Review. *Biological reviews of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 76, 529-572.
- Shannon, C. E., & Weiner, W. (1963). *The mathematical theory of communication*. Urbana: University Illinois Press, 125.
- Simpson, E. H. (1949). Measurement of diversity. *Nature*, 163, 688.
- Singh, A. V., & Hage, A. (2017). Wild Edible Fruits of Arunachal Pradesh. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 6, 6.
- Singh, P. (1991). Avian and mammalian evidences in Pakhui Wildlife Sanctuary in East Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh. *Arunachal Forest News*, 9(2), 1-10.
- Singh, P. (1994). Recent bird records from Arunachal Pradesh. *Forktail*, 10, 65-104.
- Sundarapandian, S. M., Chandrasekaran, S., & Swamy, P. S. (2005). Phenological behaviour of selected tree species in tropical forests at Kodayar in the Western Ghats, Tamil Nadu, India. *Current Science*, 88, 5.
- Tag, H., Jeri, L., Mingki, T., Tsering, J., & Das, A. K. (2012). Higher Plant Diversity in Pakke Wildlife Sanctuary and Tiger Reserve in East Kameng District of Arunachal Pradesh: Checklist - I. *Pleione*, 6(1), 149 - 162.
- Van Noort, S., & Rasplus, J.Y. (2004-2012). Fig web. Iziko Museums, South Africa. http://www.figweb.org/Figs_and_fig_wasps/index.htm.
- Vanitharani, J., Bharathi, B. K., Margaret, I. V., Malleshappa, H., Ojha, R. K., & Naik, K. G. A. (2009). Ficus Diversity in Southern Western Ghats: a Boon for Biodiversity Conservation. *Journal of Theoretical and Experimental Biology*, 6 (1), 69-79.